

THE PRE-COLONIAL SYSTEM OF GOVERNANCE INTRODUCED IN THE ANDIJAN UYEZD DURING THE REIGN OF THE TSARIST RUSSIA

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Annotation: The structure of the militarized administrative apparatus introduced in the Andijan district during the years of the Russian tsar's rule, from the establishment of the district to the establishment of the Soviet totalitarian regime, is shown on the basis of historical sources.

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In its subsequent one and a half thousand years of history, Turkestan held the status of a free state for only 376 years (Academician Buriboy Ahmedov). In the remaining periods, they lived under the oppression of invaders. From this, it is clear that for many years of historical development, Turkestan has been subjected to humiliation and discrimination against our people. The national liberation movements of our people against the tyranny of the Iranian Achaemenids, Greco-Macedonians, the Arab conquest, the Mongol invaders, and finally, the Tsarist colonizers remain forever in the pages of history[1.8].

The Turkestan Oblast, established in 1865, was initially part of the Orenburg Governor-Generalship, and from 1867, it was part of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship. After the final conquest of Central Asia, the territory of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship amounted to 1,533,255 sq. km, comparable in size to the territories of France, Germany, and Austria-Hungary[2.127]. On August 6, 1865, a draft temporary regulation on the administration of the Turkestan region was introduced. In the newly formed province, administrative bodies were in the hands of military commanders. In 1867, the Tsarist government approved a draft of a new regulation on the administration of Turkestan. According to this draft regulation, the Turkestan region was transformed into a separate Turkestan Governor-Generalship.

The main content of the statute was that "administrative and military power should be in the hands of one person, without separation." Konstantin Petrovich von Kaufman was appointed the first Governor-General of Turkestan. During 1865-1886, four temporary regulations on the administration of Turkestan were in effect. In 1886, Tsar Alexander III approved the Statute on the Administration of Turkestan. Amendments and additions were made to this regulation, which remained in effect until 1917. It should be especially noted that the Russian colonial administration, unlike the administration of other regions of the empire, conducted administration in Turkestan using a militarized method.

While many governorate and provincial administrations of Russia were subordinate to the Ministry of Internal Affairs, administrative bodies in Turkestan were subordinate to the Ministry of War. Military and civilian administrations were still subordinate to the Turkestan Governor-General, who was granted significant authority. Undoubtedly, the presence of armed

power in the region will have a serious impact on its further fate and development, giving it the character of a martial law"[2.129].

By order of the Governor-General of Turkestan, K.P. Kaufman, dated March 6, 1876, the Fergana region was created on the site of the conquered Kokand Khanate. The Fergana region included 7 districts: Kokand, Margilan, Andijan, Osh, Chimgan, Namangan, and Chust districts.

The Andijan uyezd was formed in 1876. The administration of the Andijan uyezd was as follows: uyezd chief, 2 junior and senior assistants, 2 clerks, 2 translators. The Andijan uyezd was divided into 5 administrative units, which, in turn, were divided into 21 volosts. The uyezd chief was considered the main link of colonial administration. It covers an area of 2-2.5 sq. m and has a population of 20,000. The chief was responsible for strict control over the district population, overseeing individuals with special duties, managing district statistics, the collection of taxes, and the city дума. He also considered complaints from local residents who were dissatisfied with the biys' court. He also conducted preliminary inquiries regarding serious crimes and divorce proceedings, as well as certain criminal and civil cases. Responsible for making court decisions, carrying out confiscation of property, and overseeing the postal and trade services. He also participated in the work of public health, trade, and other committees and commissions"[3.125].

From year to year, the number of staff in the Andijan uyezd administration increased. If in August 1877 the district administration consisted of 10 people - the head of the district, his two assistants, the manager and his two assistants, the interpreter, the district judge, the district doctor, the district midwife, then by 1901 the administrative-police administration of the Andijan district consisted of 17 people: the head of the district, his assistant, 5 district bailiffs, the police bailiff, the secretary, two mail carriers, the interpreter, the district doctor, the city doctor, the midwife, the city architect, the district land surveyor[3.127-128].

As noted in Muhammad Aziz Marg'iloniy's "Tarixiy Aziziy," the Andijan uyezd was formed in 1876, headed by Smirnov (Semenov in other sources). In one of the archival sources, it is noted that the head of the Andijan uyezd was Lieutenant Colonel Koshiyevsky, from August 8, 1866, he served in a military unit as a warrant officer, from March 6, 1876, he served as a senior assistant to the head of the Andijan uyezd, was fluent in the Uzbek language, and was able to freely write in the local language. In short, the first head of the Andijan uyezd was Smirnov. On the map ("Map of the Andijan Uyezd of the Fergana Oblast") compiled by the district surveyor V. Kolodovkin in 1890, the Andijan Uyezd included the volosts of Balykchi, Naryn, Khakulobod, Izboskan, Altynkul, Hakan, Yarboshi, Maygir, Novkent, Kokandkyshlak, Bazarkurgan, Aim, Kurgantepa, Karasuv, Kugart, Jalalkuduk, Chankent, Jalalobod, Maylisoy, Mosi, Kenkolkoragir, Karakolsarisu[4.10-11].

The book "Reference of Addresses of the Fergana Region," published in 1912 under number PYA-8587, kept in the rare manuscript fund of the Alisher Navoi Library, contains valuable information about the officials who governed the Andijan uyezd during the colonial period. According to the information in it, in 1908 the head of the Andijan uyezd was Yulian Aldrovich Brzhezitskiy, his deputy was Ya.E. Polyudov, his secretary was I.V. Novoselov, the postman was F.D. Rishkov, the clerk was P.A. Arkhipov, and the interpreter was Isa Tergiusizov. District doctor Osip Mikhailovich Ordinets, paramedic M.I. Nosenko, midwife A.P. Vladimirova, veterinarian N.K. Zakharov[5.25-29].

The chief of police for the first precinct of Andijan city was A.K. Kolesinsky, the chief of police for the second precinct was A.B. Mikhailov, and the chief of police for the third precinct was N.N. Cherkes; the position of chief city elder (oqsoqol) was temporarily vacant. The elder of the Uyluq quarter (daha) was Abduqodir Xojiyev, the elder of the Olayliq quarter was Zahiriddin Mahsudov, and the elder of the Qirliq quarter was Abduqahhor Orziqulbekov. This indicates that during the period in question, the Andijan uyezd was divided into three quarters, each governed by an elder. The head of the city's economic administration was V.T. Konkov, which included city deputies V.O. Kurovsky, A.A. Chaikin, and Yoqubali Xo'ja Xojimatov.[6. 246-259].

The city's architect Travin, doctor V.V. Kushornikov, hospital doctor G.A. Rotenberg, female doctor M.S. Golashevskaya, city paramedic P.P. Kuptsov, hospital head G.M. Budayevsky, as well as doctors and paramedics - G.I. Markov, M.F. Petrova, L.P. Povarenkova, Bagdanova were hospital staff. The head of the land tax of the Andijan uyezd was I.F. Yakstir, the head of state property was A.F. Kopacheli, the land surveyor was A.F. Starikov, and the secretary was D.E. Konad. Lieutenant Colonel Ya.E. Polyudov for special military service. Sofia Petrovna Olifina served as the head of the city library[5.25-29].

The head of the military garrison was S.I. Petrov, the commander of the 1st company was V.I. Medvelov, the staff captain of the 2nd company was I.N. Nesterenko, the junior officer was N.A. Vartanyans, the head of the grocery store was Yanin, the engineer was A.N. Vostokov. In the new city of Andijan, there was a four-class school, the teacher-inspector of which was N.G. Pavlov, and the teachers were V.F. Polivanny, P.A. Naumov. The director of the men's school was Kh.M. Belov, the teachers were E.P. Petrov, L.V. Kotovich, the head of the women's school was O.P. Kovalevskaya, the teachers were M.I. Kolchinskaya, N.D. Merzikova, the head of the Russo-native school was D.K. Nazarov, the teacher was Sayidboy Sharifboyev. In the judicial and legal system of the Andijan uyezd, there were N.N. Alekhin, M.S. Gnyazdovsky, V.N. Kuznetsov, A.I. Brezgunov, F.F. Levitsky, T.G. Dryakhlov, E.P. Lenzen, B.V. Levinson, G.S. Yachnik, A.A. Brotsin. The head of the post and telegraph office of the Andijan uyezd was F.Kh. Zinberg. The head of the State Bank department was N.E. Engelgart, and the treasurer was A.G. Vvedensky. The manager of the Siberian Bank in the city was D.L. Aronson, the manager of the Azovsky Bank was L.B. Kherumyan, the director of the Moscow Bank was K.Z. Sechkin, the manager of the Moscow Commercial Bank was A.I. Artelsh, the director of the Russo-Asian Bank was V.Ya. Komarovsky. The head of the Andijan city railway station was P.E. Kupikov, his assistants V.M. Donchenko, P.F. Petrov, the head of the depot N.A. Yeremeev, the doctor A.I. Beloguzhev, the head of the material sanatorium S.I. Ponushko, the ticket cashier M.N. Portnykh, the goods cashier P.S. Sherstobitov, the unloader and loader, the palace inspector G.I. Andreev, the head of the railway service Batorskiy, the building inspector P.V. Rebreev, and the telegraph operator A.G. Andreev. Faina Ivanovna Brzhezitskaya, the wife of the district head Yu. A. Brzhezitsky, was the chairwoman of the Andijan branch of the "Turkiston" society for the benefit of the needy of the region[6.246-251].

The administration of the Andijan uyezd consisted of the uyezd chief, his two senior and junior assistants, city chiefs, the head of the volost, the ober-officer (junior officer), and the pristav of the district (department).

Under the jurisdiction of the Andijan uyezd chief, there were district pristav, mahalla elders, ellikboshi, onboshi, deputies of the city community, mirobboshi, ariq oqsoqoli, mirshabboshi, qurboshi (mirshab service), and young men - mirshabs.

From 1876 until the October Revolution of 1917, the entire population of the Andijan uyezd was governed by the uyezd head through unlimited rights and powers. The uyezd chief was directly subordinate to the military governor of the Fergana region. In conclusion, during the colonial period of Tsarist Russia, they kept the people under military pressure and implemented their colonial policy, orders, and instructions. The needs and demands of the people were not taken into account. It was mainly a military-controlled, militarized uyezd.

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